

The influence of wet feed distribution on the density, growth rate and growth variability of *Tenebrio molitor*

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Calculation from volume to weight

Conversion from length and width to weight of the individual mealworms was based on the following formula: $\log_{10}(\text{weight}) = 0.9881 * \log_{10}(\text{volume}) - 0.1478$. This formula is based on a linear regression of the average weight of each zone fitted to the average volume of the individually measured mealworms (R^2 0.99).

Figure S1. The average weight of each zone with the average volume of the mealworms in that zone.

Experimental design plots

Figure S2. The different combinations between distance to wet feed and the initial weight at the start of the experimental week. Left: experiment 1; Right: experiment 2.

Dichotomous weight distribution

Example of dichotomous distribution of the individual weight of the mealworms (only observed in experiment 1).

An example from week 8 to 9 in the first experiment in the last zone. This clearly shows the two groups of mealworms that were present in a non-normally distributed pattern. The weight of the biggest mealworms was calculated directly, the weight of the smaller mealworms was estimated based on the formula above.

Figure S3. The individual weights of one zone in experiment one.

AIC of the different GAM models

Table S1. The Akaike information criterions (AICs) of the different generalised additive modelling (GAM) models with single parameters, combined or the interaction. A lower AIC indicates an improved model.

<i>Parameter</i>	experiment	Weight	Distance	Weight + distance	Weight x distance
<i>Density</i>	1	218	102	101	-98
<i>Density</i>	2	160	32	32	-147
<i>Growth</i>	1	2006	1885	1852	1739
<i>Growth</i>	2	1958	1942	1869	1786
<i>Biomass</i>	1	353	240	227	-35
<i>Biomass</i>	2	433	128	96	-104
<i>Growth variability</i>	1	1522	1603	1465	1322
<i>Growth variability</i>	2	-424	-212	-429	-487

Supporting information on the density models

This segment contains:

- 1) Predictions vs observed graphs for the density models,
- 2) Normalized graphs with a weight up to 30 mg,
- 3) Week by week comparisons of the distance to the wet feed.

The predictions versus the observations for the density models.

Figure S4. predicted vs observed graphs for density estimations. Left: experiment 1 and Right: experiment 2.

Figure S5. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the density (%/cm) for experiment 1. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S6. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the density of the mealworms in experiment 1. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the iso density line. The authors are aware that the assumption of normality was not valid in all cases.

Figure S7. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the density (%/cm) for experiment 2. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S8. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the density of the mealworms in experiment 2. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the iso density line. The authors are aware that the assumption of normality was not valid in all cases.

Supporting information on the growth models

This segment contains:

- 1) Predictions vs observed graphs for the growth models,
- 2) Normalized graphs with a weight up to 30 mg,
- 3) Week by week comparisons of the distance to the wet feed.

The predictions versus the observations for the growth models.

Figure S9. Predicted vs observed graphs for the growth rate models. Left: experiment 1 and Right: experiment 2.

Figure S10. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the growth rate of the mealworms normalized to the growth rate in the first 0-2.5 cm for experiment 1. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S11. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the growth rate of the mealworms in experiment 1. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the 0 growth line.

Figure S12. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the growth rate of the mealworms normalized to the growth rate in the first 0-2.5 cm for experiment 2. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S13. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the growth rate of the mealworms in experiment 2. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the 0 growth line.

Supporting information on the biomass models

This segment contains:

- 1) Predictions vs observed graphs for the biomass models,
- 2) Normalized graphs with a weight up to 30 mg,
- 3) Week by week comparisons of the distance to the wet feed.

The predictions versus the observations for the biomass models.

Figure S14. Predicted vs observed graphs for the biomass models. Left: experiment 1 and Right: experiment 2.

Figure S15. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the biomass distribution (%/cm) of the mealworms in experiment 1. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S16. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the biomass of the mealworms in experiment 1. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the iso-biomass line. The authors are aware that the assumption of normality was not valid in all cases.

Figure S17. Influence of the initial weight and distance to the wet feed on the biomass distribution (%/cm) of the mealworms in experiment 2. The data is transformed back to the original units.

Figure S18. Visualization of the variability and week by week (W) change in the biomass of the mealworms in experiment 2. An ANOVA was used with a post hoc Tukey test to assess if the observed differences are significant (depicted by the letters). The red line indicates the iso-biomass line. The authors are aware that the assumption of normality was not valid in all cases.